

The History and Future of Data Citation

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When preparing for this conference, I was asked to write a 1200 word abstract summarizing a complex and nuanced topic. I was then asked to present all that information in 10 minutes. Even after being allotted 15 minutes, I struggled with slides and summarizing, so I wrote a speech. I hope I can at least offer an overview and a teaser and intrigue some of you enough for more follow up. You can find the text of this talk at the link on the slide. The document also includes a growing bibliography.

And props to my co-authors who keep me grounded and technically accurate.

We begin by asserting that data citation helps make data more FAIR (the acronym) and fair (the actual word). That is to say, citation helps make data more findable and accessible through current scholarly communication systems, i.e. papers in journals. It aids reusability by providing the descriptive context of evidence behind an assertion. And it helps credit the intellectual effort necessary to create a good data set and also provides accountability for that data.

So data citation generally makes things more fair for everyone involved in doing good science.

Data citation is not new. It is a fundamental concept based on the scientific method, which demands that there must be recognized, verifiable, and credited evidence behind an assertion. Traditionally, we did this right in the literature through citation of printed monographs, tables, and maps. Or, if the data were small enough, they were simply included directly in the publication.

The digital age and the corresponding growth in the volume and complexity of data changed all that.

So what do we mean by data citation? CODATA and the International Council for Scientific and Technical Information (ICSTI) define it well. “Data citation is a **reference** to data for the purpose of **credit attribution** and **facilitation of access** to the data”. Furthermore, we want that access to be enabled for both humans and machines.

As we go forward, keep those two concepts in mind, credit and access, and the two audiences, humans and machines.

The modern concept of data citation first emerged at the turn of the millennium. For example, NASA’s Earth science archives (the DAACs) agreed to a common approach and the US Geological Survey produced guidelines in 1999, but these approaches were not broadly

adopted even within NASA and USGS. Part of the issue was that journals were still developing standards on how to cite electronic resources in general. The DOI first emerged in the year 2000, even though the underlying Handle system was almost as old as the web.

Overall, in those early digital years, data were rarely cited and if they were, the mechanisms were erratic and inconsistent.

From the mid-2000s there was growing consensus on the use of registered, resolvable, authority-based persistent identifiers (PIDs). Not only for papers but also other digital artifacts, notably data. DOIs emerged as the PID of choice for many publishers and data repositories, but there are other popular choices, especially in the life sciences.

Data started getting DOIs in 2004 and DataCite was established in December 2009, with the explicit global mission of minting DOIs for data. The concept of data “publication” was getting some legs. And even those of us who questioned that paradigm fully supported formal reference and credit for data. This support **and a lot of community activity** culminated with the broadly endorsed *Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles* in 2014. This declaration defined the core purposes and general practices of data citation. But this was an agreement of the library, data, and information science communities. The research community remained largely unaware.

So meanwhile, data were rarely cited, and if they were, the mechanisms were erratic and inconsistent. Part of the reason for this is that, from the researcher’s point of view, making data FAIR involves reuse. While large scale satellite imagery may be reused a lot, many if not most data from more localized studies may never be reused; at least not until the community as a whole recognizes that aggregating these data globally is necessary in order to make further progress. It appears a culture of data citation must be preceded by a culture of re-use.

In the last few years, there has been a lot of activity to promote data citation and to define specific guidelines for both data and software citation in Force11, RDA, the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), and the Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP). As you heard in the earlier talk on Enabling FAIR, all Earth and space science publishers are beginning to require data citation. It appears we are approaching the critical mass for a broad behavioral shift. We are optimistic that data (and software) citation is emerging as a norm for observational science.

But several issues remain and are still active areas of research. Much of this is rooted in the fact that we are taking a concept implemented for literature and human beings and trying to use it to address multiple concerns for both humans and machines.

The first issue is around citing precise subsets of very dynamic data. This is the “specific and verifiable” principle of the Joint Declaration. Repositories can have very different approaches to versioning their data and how they recommend citing different versions. They also package data and assign PIDs at very different levels of granularity.

RDA produced a Recommendation on citing specific subsets of very dynamic data. The basic idea is to assign and maintain a persistent ID to a specific, time-stamped query of a data set, as well as an ID for the data set as a whole. This appears to be the best current approach, and it is getting broader adoption, but it is definitely not the norm across all repositories. Many

simply don't have the capacity to implement it yet, and maintaining access to these cited queries through technology cycles can be quite challenging. You can find out more and hear the latest progress at their RDA Working Group session Tuesday at noon.

There are other approaches for citing dynamic data recommended by ESIP and DCC, but they are more appropriate for relatively static data.

A second issue is deciding what constitutes a first-class object in scholarly discourse. Data are only truly useful if they are accompanied with detailed documentation about their uncertainties and relevant applications. Various data journals have emerged to provide peer-review of data and documentation and to publish so-called data papers. They have different approaches however on what is to be cited—the document, the data, or both. They also differ in how they structure the information for humans and machines. Some organizations are now developing well-structured, machine-readable “publications” that provide the best services of both publishers and data repositories. A good example is the [WholeTale](#) project which is led by Globus, DataOne, and some publishers to implement what they call living and reproducible data papers. Talk to Matt Jones about this.

Data papers also try to address another concern — providing recognizable credit for data authors or creators. Data can have many important uses outside of research publications, though, so people are exploring better ways to track the impact of data. A leader in that area is the [Make Data Count](#) project which is defining consistent ways to track data reuse. They had a workshop earlier today. Other initiatives such as Project [CRedit](#) through CASRAI and the [Transparency and Openness Principles](#) at the Center for Open Science are also looking at ways to credit different contributors in different ways.

Another concern related to both credit and understanding is to identify and trace connections between all sorts of research objects (data, literature, software, people, organizations, algorithms, etc). Multiple efforts try to address this. You may have heard of the [Scholix](#) initiative which emerged out of RDA to more formally interconnect data and literature. Impressively, it is already in operation, but it is largely dependent on established citation hubs like DataCite, CrossRef, and OpenAire. We think more decentralized, Web-based mechanisms may allow more adaptability and extensibility. There is work in ESIP to explore how we might make better use of [schema.org](#) to identify and link data and other resources. ESIP is also exploring another W3C standard called [Linked Data Notifications](#) — a sort of RSS-style protocol to request and receive notifications about activities, interactions, and new information. The notification itself is an individual entity with its own URI.

Another protocol we're exploring in RDA is the [Digital Object Interface Protocol](#), which assigns a persistent ID to any digital object and allows that object to express what type of object it is and what operations it allows such as various web services or basic management functions. It's early days, but I think this has lots of potential. Check out the Data Fabric Interest Group, Tuesday at 2:00 to learn more.

Indeed, this whole interconnecting issue is a big deal and there will be a Birds-of-a-feather session on the “Research Data Graph” at RDA on Wednesday at 2:30 to discuss it further.

Finally, is the issue and concern of identity itself. People are beginning to rethink how identifiers work. To date, the basic issue of persistence of locators on the web has been addressed by what we might call authority-based identifiers, which separate the identity of an object from its location and are maintained in trusted registries. Jens Klump, in particular, has a couple good articles on the use of DOIs for data over the last couple decades, which raise some interesting issues around identity, institutional commitment, and cost models. He notes “The focus of the DOI for the data community on paper-like documents and human actors has left some conceptual gaps.” He argues, we need to explore more advanced features such as identifier templates, more sophisticated content negotiation when resolving identifiers, more machine actionability in general, as well as the social process of persistence.

In other work, data managers are looking to content-based identifiers (i.e., cryptographic-hash-based IDs) to identify exact copies of data, ideally without relying on third parties and external administrative processes. These content-based identifiers can be deployed and resolved in peer-to-peer environments like the InterPlanetary File System ([IPFS](#)) and [Dat](#). There is already an established system called [Qri](#) (query) which allows users to reference, browse, download, create, fork, and publish datasets with a broad network of peers in IPFS. It is still not well-suited to massive volumes of streaming data, and there is still the issue that different representations of data may be scientifically equivalent but not identical. (The hash really needs to include the provenance chain as well as the data set.) Nonetheless, these approaches show great promise. More importantly, content-based IDs have quite different properties from authority-based IDs. Di Cosmo and colleagues make a good argument for why we need both. We probably do.

So in summary, the world of data citation is complex and evolving. We have made substantial progress in recent years, but we need to rethink some of our assumptions. An early driver of data citation is that it would increase recognition of data authors and motivate open data sharing. That hasn’t played out.

We are also overdue in separating and explicitly addressing the myriad concerns embedded in data citation. We know, in principle, why to cite data and how to do it in many cases. Now we need to accelerate the implementation and start to address the challenging details that allow us to separate those concerns and make the best use of computers to make data both FAIR and fair.

I close by noting that ESIP has begun a new “[Research Object Citation Cluster](#)” to explore these and other issues. Everyone is welcome to join.

Thank you.

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